

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE 2014 PARLIAMENTARY
ELECTIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation

This article describes the specific features of the parliamentary elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan held on December 21, 2014, and their differences from previous parliamentary elections. In particular, the conduct of the elections is based on the "Law on Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

Key words: Oliy Majlis, parliament, election, democracy, representation, party, authority, law, collegial, electoral district, polling station, deputy, project, bulletin, Eco-Movement, charter

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Qonunchilik palatasiga 2014-yil 21-dekabr kuni bo'lib o'tgan parlament saylovlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, oldingi parlament saylovlaridan farqli jihatlari bayon etilgan. Bunda ayniqsa saylovlarning o'tkazilishi "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisga saylov to'g'risidagi Qonun" bilan asoslangan.

Аннотации

В статье рассматриваются особенности парламентских выборов в Законодательную палату Олий Мажлиса Республики Узбекистан, состоявшихся 21 декабря 2014 года, и их отличия от предыдущих

парламентских выборов. В частности, проведение выборов осуществляется на основе «Закона о выборах в Олий Мажлис Республики Узбекистан».

Kalit so'zlar: Oliy Majlis, parlament, saylov, demokratiya, vakillik, partiya, vakolat, qonun, kollegial, saylov okrugi, saylov uchastkasi, deputat, loyiha, byulliten, Ekoharakat, nizom

Ключевые слова: Олий Мажлис, парламент, выборы, демократия, представительство, партия, власть, закон, коллегиальный, избирательный округ, избирательный участок, депутат, проект, бюллетень, Экодвижение, устав

In any democratic and legal state, elections are the most important political reality and serve as the main tool for determining the further development of the country. The formation of the main legislative power of the state through elections is a sign that constitutional freedoms have been fully established in the country. The most important aspect of elections is that citizens elect their legal representatives who participate in the management of state affairs. This is the main form of indirect democracy. This norm is also reflected in the constitution of our country: "Only the Oliy Majlis and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan elected by them may act on behalf of the people of Uzbekistan" [1]. In Uzbekistan, all work on the organization and conduct of elections and ensuring the rights and freedoms of voters is carried out by election commissions authorized by law.

In our country, the next elections to the legislative chamber of the Oliy Majlis were held on December 21, 2014. In accordance with Article 19 of the Law on Elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan announces that the election campaign process has begun on September 15 of the same year. We will dwell on how these elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and regional, district and city councils of people's deputies differed from previous elections and in what aspects they were distinguished from

previous election processes. As is known, on November 12, 2010, our first President Islam Karimov delivered a report on the “Concept of Further Deepening Democratic Reforms and Developing Civil Society in Our Country” at a joint session of the Legislative Chamber and Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This report covered six major areas, the fourth of which was called “Ensuring freedom of the right to vote and developing electoral legislation in Uzbekistan.” The parliamentary elections held in 2014 were held on the basis of changes introduced based on the ideas expressed in this concept. They were as follows:

First: In accordance with the election legislation, new norms are proposed for the publication and sharing of pre-election public opinion poll results with the public. “It is considered appropriate to introduce a norm that prohibits the publication (publication) of the results of public opinion polls, election outcome forecasts and other studies related to the ongoing elections within five days before the voting day, as well as on the voting day, as well as their placement on public information and telecommunication networks (including the Internet)”[2]. The purpose of introducing this norm was to avoid distracting voters during the election, not to give preference to any political party or candidate, and to create equal opportunities for everyone on election day.

Secondly: As is known, since the 2009 elections to the Legislative Chamber, deputies to the Legislative Body from the Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan began to be elected. The concept also focused on the elections of these deputies, and it was proposed to conduct the elections of deputies elected from the Ecological Movement in a more open and transparent manner. “I believe that it would be appropriate to add an amendment to Article 6 of the Law on Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which would establish the right of observers to participate in conferences on the election of deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan”[3]. Of course,

the elections of deputies elected from the Ecomovement are also an important process, and the involvement of international observers in it will serve to make the elections more democratic.

The next major process in the electoral process is the formation of electoral districts. "According to Article 12 of the Law on Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the District Election Commission is established by the Central Election Commission no later than seventy days before the elections, consisting of the chairman, deputy chairman, secretary and at least six other members of the commission. According to our legislation, candidates for membership in district election commissions are discussed at meetings of the Jokargi Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city Kengas of people's deputies and recommended for approval to the Central Election Commission. In this case, it is advisable to select candidates for membership in district election commissions from among citizens with sufficient work experience, from among authoritative representatives of society. Thus, "1462 people were involved in district election commissions. 45.1 percent of them are representatives of the education sector, 21.8 percent are representatives of public associations, non-governmental non-profit organizations, 8.1 percent are representatives of the healthcare system, and 36 percent are representatives of the production sector. 66.9 percent of commission members have previously participated in the preparation and conduct of elections. The number of women is 20.1 percent" [4]. One of the most important norms of this process is that, in order to make the electoral process more fair, candidates for district election commissions cannot be members of any political party. The education and academic degrees of district commission members are also taken into account.

On election day, almost all citizens of our country were able to make a worthy contribution to the future prospects and well-being of our Motherland. Voters actively participated in the elections and voted for the candidates they

considered worthy. This is also proven by the numbers. “The names of 20 million 789 thousand 572 voters were included in the voter list in our country, and 18 million 490 thousand 245 or 88.94 percent of voters participated in the elections”[5]. Of course, the first of the main reasons for such active participation of voters is the increasing legal awareness and culture of our citizens, their ability to boldly express their position on the ongoing political and legal processes, and the second reason is the conditions created for voters visiting the relevant polling stations. After all, they can be shown a medical room equipped with all the necessary medicines, a mother and child room for mothers with young children to visit, etc. Now let's move directly to the election results. “According to the results of the voting, deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan were elected in 113 electoral districts. 47 of them are from the Movement of Entrepreneurs and Businessmen - the Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, 28 from the Democratic Party of Uzbekistan “Milliy Tiklanish”, 21 from the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan and 17 from the Social Democratic Party of Uzbekistan “Adolat” [6]. As a result of the long-term pre-election preparations, citizens voted for the candidates and political parties they considered worthy. Any country that cares about its future and development, of course, relies on the laws, rules and principles of democracy in the organization of state administration and state power. After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan set itself the main goal of building a legal, democratic country and establishing a civil society, and chose the path of democracy in organizing state power. “Article 45 of the Law on Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan introduces the concept of repeat voting, which states that if at least two candidates are nominated in an electoral district, but none of them is elected, a repeat voting may be organized between the two candidates who received the most votes. It is stipulated that repeat voting shall be held within two weeks after the election in compliance with the requirements of the Law. Based on this provision

of the Law, “On December 25, 2014, by Resolution No. 658 of the Central Election Commission, repeat voting was determined in 22 electoral districts holding repeat voting to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan” [7]. Repeat voting, like the main elections, is conducted based on the requirements of relevant regulatory legal acts. Observers and media representatives are also invited to it. The reason is that repeat voting is also a component of the election. “On January 4, 2015, 3,434,345 voters were registered in 1,472 polling stations in 22 constituencies holding a repeat vote for the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, of which 2,642,063 voters participated in the repeat vote. This is 76.9 percent of the total number of voters in 22 constituencies holding a repeat vote for the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.”[8] According to Article 45 of the Law “On Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, a candidate participating in a repeat vote, unlike in the main election, does not have to receive more than half of the votes of voters, but is considered to be elected as a candidate for deputy if he receives more votes than another candidate. One of the most important aspects of the repeat vote is that the percentage of voter turnout is not taken into account. “According to the final results of the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 150 deputies were elected to the lower house of parliament, including 52 from the Movement of Entrepreneurs and Businessmen - the Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, 36 from the Democratic Party of Uzbekistan “Milliy Tiklanish”, 27 from the People’s Democratic Party of Uzbekistan and 20 from the Social Democratic Party of Uzbekistan “Adolat”. 15 deputies are representatives of the Ecological Movement of Uzbekistan. 24 or 16 percent of the elected deputies are women”[9]. Thus, according to the results of the parliamentary elections, we can see that the share of women in state power is increasing year by year. The international community certainly highly appreciates this situation. Most importantly, during this election

period, elections were held on the basis of democratic requirements, with full compliance with the principles of transparency and openness. So, in the social composition of the elected deputies, we can see our compatriots of various professions. Among them, representatives of the educational sphere, lawyers and economists are especially in the majority. "In this election, our young deputies are in the majority compared to the previous one. For example, 11 deputies are citizens under the age of 30. If we look at the nationality of the deputies elected to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 133 are Uzbeks, 7 are Karakalpaks, 4 are Russians, 2 are Tajiks, 3 are Kazakhs and 1 is Korean. Of those registered for deputies, 40 were deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the previous convocation" [10]. If we pay attention to the results of the parliamentary elections this year, we see that the share of deputies under the age of thirty has increased. This is evidence that the state policy regarding youth in our country is being implemented with priority. After all, as a result of the created conditions for them, they were able to be elected as deputies in the legislative branch. Also, another important aspect that deserves attention is the fact that deputies are elected from representatives of many nationalities. As we all know, Uzbekistan is a multinational country. Therefore, the election of representatives of other nationalities besides Uzbeks in the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis is a sign that our multi-ethnic people live in harmony.

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